

The Structure of Gold (III) Complex of *p*-Phenylene-di-(1-tetrazoline-5-thione) (PDT-5)

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The reaction of Au^{+3} ions with *p*-phenylene-di-(1-tetrazoline-5-thione) or 'PDT-5' has been studied in detail. The ligand, which is a newly introduced analytical reagent for copper, silver, gold, cadmium and ruthenium, reacts quantitatively with these metal ions, and gives precipitates of the corresponding complexes. The metal : ligand ratio in the gold(III) complex of PDT-5 is 1 : 1. Thus, a structure of the complex, $\text{Au}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_4\text{S}_2)\text{Cl}$, has been proposed on the basis of i.r. and magnetic studies.

The study of metal complexes where the metal ion coordinates through sulphur and nitrogen simultaneously is generally rare. Recently, in this field the structural aspects of a few transition metal complexes of certain 1-substituted tetrazoline-5-thiones¹ have been studied by means of their infra-red spectra². Whereas the work on the complexes of these monofunctional tetrazoline-5-thiones has progressed further³, no work has so far been done in evaluating the complexing behaviour of the difunctional tetrazoline-5-thiones, which are structurally more interesting compounds. The ligand chosen in our study is *p*-phenylene-di-(1-tetrazoline-5-thione) or 'PDT-5'. The reaction of PDT-5 with Au^{+3} ions has been investigated in detail. The qualitative and quantitative studies made with the ligand show that when an alcoholic or acetone solution of PDT-5 is treated at $\text{pH} < 7$ with copper (I), copper (II)⁴, and silver (I)⁵ ions in solution, light brown, deep green, and white precipitates respectively of the corresponding metal complexes are formed. At this pH range, gold (III) does not give any precipitate. However, at pH 8–11 or in the presence of an acetate buffer, gold (III) immediately reacts with the ligand, giving an orange coloured precipitate of the gold complex. The present communication deals with the preparation, general study, elemental, and infrared spectral analysis of the gold (III) complex of PDT-5.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Ligand : The ligand, PDT-5, (Fig. 1a) was prepared by the method described by Lieber and Slutkin⁶.

Preparation of the Gold (III) Complex of PDT-5 : 0.6 g. of gold (III) chloride (Johnson-Matthey and Co., London) was dissolved in 100 ml. of distilled water containing 2 g. of ammonium acetate. An excess of 1% ligand solution in warm acetone was then added,

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3. U. Agarwala and S. K. Dikshit, *J. inorg. nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1245.
4. U. Agarwala and G. S. Johar, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1969, **32**, 339.
5. U. Agarwala and G. S. Johar, *Curr. Sci.*, 1969, **38**, 139.
6. E. Lieber and R. Slutkin, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 2214.

and the contents stirred gently. An orange coloured precipitate of gold (III) complex that immediately formed, was filtered, washed with acetone, and dried in a vacuum desiccator or in an air oven at 110°. Yield was \simeq 1 g.

The orange coloured gold complex is a non-crystalline and thermally quite stable solid. Its decomposition point is around 300°. The complex is insoluble in water, alcohol, acetone, ether, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, pyridine, and hydrocarbons. This points to its polymeric nature. Dilute and fairly concentrated mineral acids and alkalies are also without effect on it.

The composition of the gold (III) complex as established by micro analysis shows that the metal : ligand ratio is 1 : 1. The empirical formula is thus, $\text{Au}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{N}_8\text{S}_2)\text{Cl}$. Found : Au, 38.02; C, 18.95; H, 0.88; N, 22.31; Cl, 6.59; Calcd. for $\text{Au}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{N}_8\text{S}_2)\text{Cl}$: Au, 38.72; C, 18.88; H, 0.78; N, 22.01; Cl, 6.96.

In an attempt to establish the structure of the gold complex, its infrared absorption spectrum was recorded in the region of 4000–400 cm^{-1} on a Perkin-Elmer Grating Spectrophotometer (Model 521) in potassium bromide disc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

From the analytical data above, it appears that the stoichiometry of the gold (III) complex of PDT-5 is essentially $\text{Au}(\text{Ligand})\text{Cl}$. Since in the ligand molecule both the tetrazoline-5-thionyl groups have one replaceable hydrogen each, the metal can form either a simple salt by linking with one nitrogen atom² or an inner complex by forming bonds with both nitrogen and sulphur. The examination of the infrared spectra of the complex and the ligand, however, reveal the inner complex-type structure being present in it. The major changes in the spectrum of the complex from that of the ligand are as follows :

(a) The H–N–C = S bands⁷ of the ligand due to mixed vibrations of $\nu(\text{C} = \text{S})$, $\nu(\text{C} - \text{N})$, $\delta(\text{N} - \text{H})$, and $\delta(\text{C} - \text{H})$ at 1500 cm^{-1} , 1310 cm^{-1} , 990 cm^{-1} , and 760 cm^{-1} shift from their original positions and four new bands around 1110 cm^{-1} , 1035 cm^{-1} , 560 cm^{-1} , and 405 cm^{-1} appear in the spectrum of the complex. 1110 cm^{-1} and 1035 cm^{-1} bands may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C} - \text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C} = \text{S})$ modes of vibrations respectively. However, it may be possible that these bands may not be due to pure $\nu(\text{C} - \text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C} = \text{S})$, but may be having contributions from both the modes of vibrations. This indicates that the mixing of $\nu(\text{C} = \text{S})$, $\nu(\text{C} - \text{N})$, and $\delta(\text{C} - \text{H})$ is disturbed when the hydrogen of the N–H group of the ligand is replaced by the metal ion or/and when the thiocarbonyl sulphur is coordinated to the metal ion. The new bands at 560 cm^{-1} and 405 cm^{-1} have been assigned to $\nu(\text{Au} - \text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{Au} - \text{S})$ respectively.

(b) The disappearance of the band at 760 cm^{-1} , which is essentially due to $\nu(\text{C} = \text{S})$ mode as pointed out by Suzuki⁸ indicates the Au–S bond in the complex.

(c) The band at 3040 cm^{-1} is present in the spectrum of the ligand as well as in that of the gold complex. However, the intensity of this band in the complex is very much smaller than that in the ligand. The assignment of this band in the ligand is made to the superposition of $\nu(\text{N} - \text{H})$ and $\nu(\text{C} - \text{H})$ ⁹. The considerable lowering of intensity of this band in

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the complex with respect to that in the ligand is attributed to the absence of (N-H) bond in the complex.

Thus, it is concluded from the elemental analysis and infrared studies of the gold complex that the gold ion is probably coordinated through both thiocarbonyl sulphur and the (tetrazoline) nitrogen atoms of the ligand.

Because of the structure of the two complex forming moieties present in the ligand molecule, the latter is expected to form a polymeric complex¹⁰. This view is supported by : (i) the extreme insolubility of the complex in water and most other common organic solvents, and (ii) its fairly high thermal stability, and chemical resistance towards mineral acids and alkalis.

Thus, on the basis of above findings, and in consistence with the infrared spectra, the following zigzag-type polymeric structure is suggested for the gold complex (Fig. 1b).

Fig. 1
a.....Ligand
b.....Complex

In this structure of the gold complex, the gold (III) ion with coordination number five, is assumed to have tetrahedral arrangement of the ligand around itself (and in general, gold (III) prefers to form tetrahedral complexes).

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